

The Tomb of Khnumhotep I at Beni Hassan

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The site of Beni Hassan is located approximately 20 km south of modern el-Minya, Egypt. It consists of a cemetery of rock-cut tombs that were carved across the late Third to the early Second Millennium BCE, or the late Old and Middle Kingdoms of ancient Egyptian history. A row of tombs on an upper terrace mostly features the burials of affluent individuals. They are believed to be the local ruling elite, and their families, of the 16th nome of Upper Egypt, the so-called Oryx nome. Some of their tombs have preserved remarkably detailed wall paintings representing a myriad of motifs on social, cultural, religious, and administrative activities, all of which emphasise the tomb owners' achievements, social identity, and status. One of these tombs was categorised by Nineteenth Century Egyptologists as Tomb Nr. 14, its wall scenes revealing that it belonged to a 'great overlord of the Oryx nome' who served the first pharaoh of the Middle Kingdom's Twelfth Dynasty, King Amenemhat I. This overlord was named Khnumhotep.

Date Range: 1992 BCE - 1956 BCE

Region: Beni Hassan

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Egypt, Egypt, Beni Hassan

The site of Beni Hassan is located approximately 20 km south of modern el-Minya. Its cemetery includes Third to Second Millennium BCE burials belonging to those who lived in a local community ascribed to the 16th Upper Egyptian Oryx nome of ancient Egypt.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Newberry, P.E. 1893. Beni Hasan, part I. Archaeological Survey of Egypt. London.
- Source 2: Lashien, M. and Mourad, A.-L. 2019. Beni Hassan, vol. V: The Tomb of Khnumhotep I. The Australian Centre for Egyptology Reports 43. Oxford.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://benihassan.com/>

– Source 1 Description: The website follows the archaeological work and research at Beni Hassan and its burials as conducted by Macquarie University and The Australian Centre for Egyptology. It includes a Visual Dictionary for the inscribed tombs, as well as other resources on the site.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:
– Year range: Explorations include those of 1890-1893 and 2016-2017.

↳ Name of excavation
– Official or descriptive name: 1890-1893: Archaeological Survey of Egypt; 2016-2017: The Australian Centre for Egyptology, Macquarie University, under the directorship of Naguib Kanawati

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation
– Rock face

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature
– Leveling of ground
– Clearing

Notes: The tomb featured a cleared forecourt at its entrance, and a large chapel within which were originally two pillars cut from the native limestone, and two burial shafts carved into its floor.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are few archaeological remains of settlements linked with the Oryx nome, of which Beni Hassan was a part. Some tomb inscriptions at the site mention towns in its vicinity, such as Menaat-Khufu, but their exact location remains unknown.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: The tomb featured a cleared forecourt at its entrance, and a large rectangular chapel within which were originally two pillars cut from the native limestone, and two burial shafts carved into its floor.

A group of structures:

– No

A group of features:

– Yes

Notes: The tomb featured a cleared forecourt at its entrance, and a large rectangular chapel within which were originally two pillars cut from the native limestone, and two burial shafts carved into its floor.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

Notes: The tomb of Khnumhotep I is part of a cemetery of burials.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

–Other [specify]: As a burial place, the tomb was also a memorial, representative of Khnumhotep I's social identity and status, and likely providing a place for commemoration or offerings for the deceased by those within his immediate family, social group and/or community.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

Notes: Across the ceiling, floor, and walls of the tomb's chapel are several tethering marks of uncertain date. They were perhaps used to rope animals or vessels. At some point in antiquity, the tomb's original pillars were also removed, likely intentionally.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: The tomb's original pillars were possibly intentionally removed in antiquity.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: The exact purpose of the pillars' removal is uncertain. as is the

date when this occurred.

Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: No, the pillars likely required intentional force to be removed.

Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: According to Egyptian beliefs, the ka (soul) of the tomb owner and another individual buried in the tomb, perhaps his wife, may have inhabited its space.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– Private individual

Notes: The tomb's construction was likely commissioned by the tomb owner himself and/or members of his family, although direct evidence for this from the tomb is absent.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Priests

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: A diverse group of individuals were likely involved in organising, designing, constructing,

and decorating the tomb.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Notes: Elements of the tomb could have been gifted or sponsored by the king or central administration, but no direct evidence for this exists.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Funerary beliefs and practices

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– No

Notes: Wooden elements, such as doors, are attested in texts referring to tomb architecture of the period. However, none have survived in this particular structure.

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: The tomb is rock-cut into the native, good-quality white limestone of the mountain. It featured a cleared forecourt at its entrance, and a large rectangular chapel within which were originally two pillars cut from the native limestone, and two burial shafts also cut into its floor.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The tomb is rock-cut into the native, good-quality white limestone of the mountain. It featured a cleared forecourt at its entrance, and a large rectangular chapel within which were originally two pillars cut from the native limestone, and two burial shafts also cut into its floor.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: While the ceiling of the tomb's chapel is devoid of decoration, its walls are all decorated with painted scenes and texts. Although poorly preserved, these include scenes showing offering bearers, workshop and agricultural activities, fishing, fowling, wine making, hunting desert animals, dancing, as well as militaristic activities, including a siege.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

Notes: No external inscriptions have been preserved.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

Notes: Deities are mentioned in the tomb's hieroglyphic texts.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

Notes: None preserved.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

Notes: None preserved.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The top of all walls of the tomb's chapel preserve traces of a frieze above a colourful, horizontal banded frieze. The west, north and east walls also preserve vertical friezes.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: The paintings were possibly applied in al secco technique.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

Notes: The west wall of the tomb preserves a hieroglyphic text of the tomb owner's biography, with details of his achievements and historical events. The wall paintings otherwise include representations of individuals encountered, and perhaps events experienced, in the tomb owner's lifetime.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The paintings preserve a variety of scenes, including those showing offering bearers, workshop and agricultural activities, fishing, fowling, wine making, hunting desert animals, dancing, as well as militaristic activities, including a siege.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: The west wall of the tomb preserves a hieroglyphic text of the tomb owner's biography, with details of his achievements and historical events. Other texts featured in the tomb include dedicatory texts or invocations, offering formulae, the names, titles and epithets of individuals, as well as captions to particular scenes or details.

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are mentioned in the hieroglyphics texts of the tomb.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is ongoing discussion if scenes in contemporaneous decorated tombs from this area, and elsewhere in Egypt, represent scenes of idealised 'daily life' activities or of an ideal afterlife. The former appears most likely.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: The west wall of the tomb preserves a hieroglyphic text of the tomb owner's biography, with details of his achievements and historical events. Other texts featured in the tomb include dedicatory texts or invocations, offering formulae, the names, titles and epithets of individuals, as well as captions to particular scenes or details.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The tomb's painted wall scenes include the so-called 'false door' on the west wall, north of the entrance.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Notes: This is dependant on how 'worship' is approached. The place was more to commemorate a deceased person(s).

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: This is dependant on how 'worship' is approached. The place was more for the commemoration of a deceased person(s).

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Notes: According to other evidence from Egypt, offerings were usually presented to the tomb owner, but no evidence for these is preserved at the tomb.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: According to other evidence from Egypt, grave goods were usually deposited in tombs of the elite, but no evidence for these is preserved at the tomb.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The tomb features two shafts leading to burial chambers. They may have belonged to the tomb owner, Khnumhotep I, and perhaps his main wife.

- ↳ Domestic context:
 - Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
 - No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

- No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

- No

Are previously human spirits present:

- Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: From other material in Egypt, human spirits may communicate with the living. However, there is no direct evidence for this at the tomb.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

- Yes

Notes: According to Egyptian beliefs, the ka (soul) of the tomb owner and another individual buried in the tomb, perhaps his wife, may have inhabited its space. The texts preserved on the tomb chapel's walls otherwise mention a number of deities worshipped in the region, including Osiris, Anubis, Hathor, Horus, Khnum, Heqat and Iwenmutef.

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is assumed, but not confirmed at the tomb.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: While no remains of sacrificed animals remain, oxen and fowl are listed in the offering formulae of the tomb's texts.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Notes: Material offerings were likely present, but none have been preserved.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: Festivals are known for the area, but none directly associated with the tomb.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

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↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Funerary rituals were likely carried out in association with the death of the tomb owner.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Preserved paintings include depictions of men represented performing recitations, censuring, or offering libations. The tomb owner, a male, also held the title of 'overseer of priests'.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: They are represented as Egyptian individuals.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: Religious specialists are assumed to be of the upper class. The tomb owner, among the local elite, was also an overseer of priests.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The tomb owner was provided with the title of 'overseer of priests'. Two other priests are mentioned in the tomb, one a so-called 'lector-priest' and the other a 'sm-priest'.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Notes: Offering formulae and invocations are preserved among the texts written on the tomb chapel's walls.

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Offering formulae and invocations are preserved among the texts written on the tomb chapel's walls.

Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Offering formulae and invocations are preserved among the texts written on the tomb chapel's walls.

Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Some prayers and invocations may have been spoken at the tomb.

Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

Notes: If similar to biographies inscribed in other tombs at the cemetery, the badly preserved biography on the west wall of the tomb's chapel perhaps also featured mention of the construction of the tomb.

Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

Notes: Offering formulae and invocations are preserved among the texts written on the tomb chapel's walls.

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

Notes: Hieroglyphic texts, including offering formulae and invocations, are written on the tomb chapel's walls.

Bibliography

General References

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